

1 **Development of a Translational Exposure-Bracketing Approach to Streamline the**
2 **Development of Hormonal Contraceptive Drug Products**

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28

29 **Abstract**

30 Worldwide, 922 million women of reproductive age (or their partners) use some sort of
31 contraception to prevent pregnancy. Oral combined hormonal contraceptives (CHC) typically
32 utilize a combination of a progestin and an estrogen. CHC are potentially at risk to metabolic drug-
33 drug interaction (DDI) via CYP3A4, the main enzyme involved in the oxidative metabolism of
34 ethinyl estradiol (EE) and most progestins, e.g. levonorgestrel (LNG) and drospirenone (DRSP).
35 Recently, the FDA issued a guidance addressing metabolic DDIs in the realm of CHC,
36 establishing an overall class-based recommendation with respect to avoidance of CYP3A4
37 induction interactions. Given that different progestins have varying magnitudes of fraction
38 metabolized by CYP3A4 ($f_{m_{CYP3A4}}$), it would be of clinical benefit to determine if all progestins are
39 at the same risk to CYP3A4-mediated metabolic DDI. LNG and DRSP are commonly used
40 progestins that are at the margins of the rifampicin induction effect observed *in vivo* since they
41 have the relatively lowest and highest $f_{m_{CYP3A4}}$ among commonly used CHC formulations
42 containing norgestimate, desogestrel, norgestrel, and norethindrone. Therefore, we applied a
43 multi-pronged strategy, i.e. (1) development of the PBPK models, (2) comparison of the effect of
44 CYP3A inducers and inhibitors on DRSP vs. LNG, and (3) providing the clinical-practice context
45 based on real world data, to explore the difference in DDI risk for oral CHCs.

46 Introduction

47 Contraceptives are commonly used among women of reproductive age (or their partners) to
48 prevent pregnancy, with an estimated prevalence of more than 922 million users worldwide.¹
49 Orally administered combined hormonal contraceptives (CHC) is a common contraceptive
50 method, that utilizes combination of a progestin and an estrogen, typically ethinyl estradiol (EE).
51 It is well known that hormonal contraceptives are at risk for metabolic drug-drug interactions
52 (DDIs) via CYP3A4, particularly for interactions with CYP3A4 inducers as outlined in the U.S.
53 Food and Drug Administration's (FDA) guidance for industry on labeling for CHC. Such risks have
54 been recently assessed for oral levonorgestrel (LNG), a common progestin with relatively low
55 fraction metabolized by CYP3A4 ($f_{m_{CYP3A4}}$) of approximately 33%. Unlike classical victim-
56 perpetrator pairwise DDI assessment, our previous work pointed out the importance of
57 considering a more complex DDI network for CHCs. These findings point to a need for considering
58 the impact of perpetrators on CYP3A4 in addition to the impact of EE, sex hormone binding
59 globulin (SHBG) levels, affinity of the victim drug to bind to SHBG, and the influence of
60 perpetrators on SHBG expression.² Since progestins differ in terms of $f_{m_{CYP3A4}}$ and affinity to
61 SHBG, significant differences in the rifampicin-mediated induction effect of CYP3A4 and SHBG
62 on systemic exposure of different progestins have already been shown clinically.³ .

63 A model-based description of these effects focusing on defining the effect limits towards upper
64 and lower boundaries of progestin $f_{m_{CYP3A4}}$ and affinity to SHBG, hereinafter referred to as
65 exposure bracketing approach, could provide significant insight into our clinical understanding of
66 all CHC drug interactions and therapeutic uses. In this context, drospirenone (DRSP), which is
67 another common progestin used within CHCs for contraceptive therapy, was selected to explore
68 limiting scenarios. DRSP's $f_{m_{CYP3A4}}$ is approximately 65%, and thus, a more significant drug
69 exposure change due to concomitant administration of CYP3A4 inducers or inhibitors is expected
70 relative to LNG. Furthermore, DRSP does not bind to SHBG. Given that all other common
71 progestins used in CHCs or oral progestin-only products (e.g. norgestimate, desogestrel,

72 norgestrel, and norethindrone) have a $f_{m_{CYP3A4}}$ and SHBG affinity between LNG and DRSP, this
73 exposure bracketing approach would improve the generalizability of DDI findings among
74 progestins.⁴

75 Physiologically-based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) modeling has proven to be a valuable tool for
76 understanding metabolic DDIs without the need for dedicated clinical trials, provided that the
77 predictive performance of such models be adequate for such purposes.⁵ While the performance
78 of LNG PBPK model has been assessed, a PBPK model describing DRSP systemic exposure is
79 not available in the public domain yet.² Thus, this work aimed to develop and validate a DRSP
80 PBPK model to inform an exposure bracketing approach intended to gain mechanistic insights
81 and assess the risks of DDIs for oral hormonal contraceptive therapies. To make a stronger
82 linkage to outcomes beyond pharmacokinetics (PK) only, we further conducted a real-world
83 evidence study to compare the rate of unintended pregnancy outcomes among women using
84 CHCs containing LNG or DRSP in co-administration with CYP3A4 inducers.

85

86

87 **Methods**

88 PBPK software and parameter estimation algorithm

89 PBPK modeling and simulation was performed in PK-Sim[®] and MoBi[®] version 9.1. Parameter
90 optimization was accomplished using the built-in Monte Carlo algorithm. PBPK platforms and
91 clinical PK data are available on Github ([https://github.com/Open-Systems-
92 Pharmacology/Hormonal-Contraceptive-Agents-Datasets](https://github.com/Open-Systems-Pharmacology/Hormonal-Contraceptive-Agents-Datasets)).

93 DRSP PBPK model development and validation

94 PBPK model development and validation were performed using a stepwise modeling analysis
95 plan (Figure 1). The DRSP-specific input parameters are summarized in Table 1. Briefly, DRSP
96 fraction metabolized by CYP3A4 (fm_{CYP3A4}), approximately 65%, was back calculated from the
97 ratio between the area under the concentration-time curve (AUC) for DRSP obtained with and
98 without co-administration of ketoconazole (strong CYP3A4 inhibitor) as observed by Wiesinger
99 and co-workers.⁶ The similarity between the total clearance values observed for DRSP
100 administered alone or in combination with ethinyl estradiol (EE) suggests that, in contrast to
101 levonorgestrel, DRSP fm_{CYP3A4} is less affected by EE when administered as a combined hormonal
102 contraceptive (CHC).⁷ DRSP's renal clearance was derived from PK data obtained in women with
103 normal or impaired renal functions.⁸ The physiologically-based disposition model was developed
104 by fitting specific CYP3A4 clearance to subject-level data following intravenous administration of
105 0.5 mg of DRSP to eight healthy, young women (age 20 – 35 years old and $18 < BMI < 25 \text{ kg/m}^2$).⁹
106 Specific intestinal permeability was fitted to individual PK profiles observed after orally
107 administering 2 mg of DRSP only formulation to the same cohort of eight healthy, young women.⁹
108 The performance of the DRSP PBPK model was externally validated against two additional
109 datasets not used to train the model, *i.e.* DRSP 2 mg administered intravenously and DRSP 3 mg
110 administered orally to six postmenopausal women (age 55 – 65 years).⁹

111 The validated DRSP PBPK model was subsequently integrated into an EE PBPK model
112 previously developed by our group.² The predictive performance of the resulting CHC PBPK
113 model was assessed by recapitulating DRSP systemic exposure after single and multiple doses
114 of the CHC (DRSP 3 mg + EE 0.03 mg QD) to young women for 21 days.

115 Finally, the adequacy of the estimated DRSP $f_{mCYP3A4}$ was further confirmed by quantitatively
116 reproducing the impact of rifampicin (strong CYP3A4 inducer) on DRSP's systemic exposure.^{3,6}
117 For this modeling exercise, we applied PBPK models for ketoconazole and rifampicin. The
118 rifampicin model has been independently developed and validated, while the ketoconazole model
119 was specifically developed for this project.¹⁰ Details concerning the ketoconazole PBPK model
120 development and validation can be found in the Supplemental Material.

121 For validation purposes, each virtual trial mimicked the design of the actual clinical trial in terms
122 of dosing and population demographics. Clinical data were analyzed via noncompartmental
123 analysis of the publicly available individual PK data for DRSP using the Phoenix™
124 Pharmacokinetic and Pharmacodynamic (PK/PD) Platform Version 8.1 (Certara, CA, USA).⁹
125 Thus, the following PK metrics and parameters were derived for DRSP: maximum plasma
126 concentrations (C_{max}), area under the plasma concentration–time curve from time 0 to the last
127 measured time point (AUC_{last}), AUC extrapolated to infinity (AUC_{inf}), clearance (CL), volume of
128 distribution at steady state (V_{ss}), apparent CL (CL/F) and apparent volume of distribution (V_z/F).
129 DRSP PBPK model performance and credibility, at internal and external levels, were assessed
130 by comparing mean model simulations (SIM) with clinical observations (OBS). Model adequacy
131 was concluded if SIM/OBS ratios for peak and extent of DRSP exposure were between 0.8 and
132 1.25. Model predictions were further validated by visually comparing simulated 95% population
133 interval to the clinically observed standard errors to assess if the models could account for
134 between subject variability in PK.

135 *Establishing Upper and Lower Bounds of Exposure Brackets for DDI Scenarios: within-compound*
136 *analysis*

137 DRSP and LNG were chosen as model drugs to represent progestins that are, respectively,
138 extensively and poorly metabolized by CYP3A4 as well as show poor and high affinity to bind to
139 SHBG in plasma.^{2,4,6} The presently validated DRSP PBPK model and previously developed LNG
140 PBPK model were combined with independently developed models for EE and strong CYP3A4
141 perpetrators (i.e., ketoconazole, carbamazepine, rifampicin, and efavirenz) to quantify the
142 maximum impact of strongly inhibiting or inducing the CYP3A4-mediated metabolic pathway on
143 systemic exposure of progestins.^{11,12} Carbamazepine and efavirenz are strong and moderate
144 CYP3A4 inducers, respectively, showing time-dependent PK due to auto-induction of their own
145 metabolism. CYP3A4 is the major metabolic pathway for carbamazepine, whereas it only plays a
146 minor role in efavirenz biotransformation, which is mainly due to CYP2B6.¹² Rifampicin is another
147 strong CYP3A4 inducer whose impact on LNG and DRSP exposure has been assessed clinically.
148 In comparison, ketoconazole is a strong CYP3A4 inhibitor.⁶

149 This model-based approach aimed at assessing the impact of DDIs relative to the $f_{mCYP3A4}$ as well
150 as the impact of dosing regimen on complex network interactions for CHCs. To this end, we
151 evaluated two different scenarios that are relevant for drug development, regulatory assessment,
152 as well as clinical practice. In scenario 1, a single oral dose of DRSP (3 mg) or LNG (0.15 mg) in
153 combination with EE (0.03 mg) was administered on Day 21 to virtual subjects who had already
154 been taking a strong inducer or inhibitor since Day 1 (i.e. perpetrator dosed to steady state prior
155 to concomitant administration of a single oral dose of the victim drug). This scenario is in
156 accordance with the current FDA Clinical Drug Interaction Studies Guidance for victim drugs not
157 showing time-dependent pharmacokinetics, i.e., auto-inhibition or auto-induction.¹³ However, EE
158 is also a competitive inhibitor of CYP3A4, which may affect the PK of progestins and perpetrators
159 that are also metabolized by CYP3A4 resulting in an intricate DDI network.¹⁴ Therefore, in
160 scenario 2, the victim progestin, EE and perpetrator were dosed to steady-state in order to
161 resemble clinical reality more closely. Oral doses of the perpetrators were chosen to mimic their
162 therapeutic usage and maximize induction/inhibition of CYP3A4 metabolic pathway. Since the
163 current validated EE PBPK model does not quantitatively address the contribution of CYP3A4 to

164 the metabolic clearance of EE in all network DDI simulations, the observed effect of
165 carbamazepine or efavirenz on EE PK was mimicked by reducing the EE dose in the CHC.^{2,4}
166 Carbamazepine 600 mg QD for 21 days reduced EE exposure by 40%; thus, EE dose in the CHC
167 was decreased from 30 µg to 18 µg. In turn, efavirenz 600 mg QD for 14 days reduced EE
168 exposure by 10%; thus, EE dose in the CHC was decreased from 30 µg to 27 µg.⁴

169 Between-compound analysis

170 A ratio approach was applied to compare the impact of CYP3A4 inducers and inhibitors on DRSP
171 and LNG exposure. Briefly, the impact of CYP3A4 inducers/inhibitors on LNG exposure was used
172 to benchmark the magnitude of CYP3A4-mediated DDI involving DRSP. This approach enabled
173 the assessment of the impact of DDIs relative to the fraction metabolized. In other words, to
174 identify potential in-class differences within extreme-case DDI scenarios, the ratio between the
175 extent of victim drug exposure with and without perpetrator (AUCR) simulated for DRSP
176 ($AUCR_{DRSP}$) and its counterpart simulated for LNG ($AUCR_{LNG}$) was calculated using the following
177 equation.

178

$$179 \quad Ratio = \frac{AUCR_{DRSP}}{AUCR_{LNG}}$$

180

181 Real-world data (RWD) analysis

182 For the real-world data comparison aspects of this study, we conducted a retrospective cohort
183 study using IBM® MarketScan® Research Databases (2005-2018) to estimate and compare
184 contraception failure rates among concomitant users of CYP3A4-inducing antiepileptic drugs and
185 CHC with DRSP or LNG components. This database provides medical encounter and pharmacy
186 claims data from a nationwide sample of private health insurance plans in the U.S.

187 We identified females of childbearing age (18-48), diagnosed with epilepsy, personality or
188 depressive mood disorder, who had concomitant use of carbamazepine, oxcarbazepine,
189 phenytoin or topiramate with combined oral contraceptives. Carbamazepine, oxcarbazepine, and
190 phenytoin have similar induction capacity (strong CYP3A4 inducers), and topiramate is a
191 weak/moderate CYP3A4 inducer. Given the induction potential for all four agents and to achieve
192 reasonable study power, we considered all four agents as potential perpetrators. Patients with
193 infertility or hormonal dysfunction diagnoses were excluded. Concomitant use was determined
194 based on information available from pharmacy dispensing data based on dispensing date and
195 pharmacy recorded days' supply. We operationalized contraception failure with an algorithm
196 previously developed by our team that uses pregnancy-related medical encounter diagnoses and
197 procedures (e.g., delivery procedure, abortion procedure, prenatal visits) to estimate pregnancy
198 start date, duration, and end date.¹⁵ We have demonstrated the ability of this algorithm to identify
199 elevated contraception failure rates in the presence of drug-drug interactions previously.¹⁶ If a
200 pregnancy start date occurred within a concomitant use episode, it was considered a
201 contraception failure event. We followed patients from the index date of concomitant use until the
202 end of concomitant use plus a minimum of 3 months to ensure detection of pregnancy and
203 backward estimation of conception for up to three years to ascertain contraception failure. We
204 measured several demographic and clinical factors that could impact failure rates during a 6-
205 month baseline period during which women were required to have continuous health plan
206 enrollment. Propensity scores that predict treatment choice were used to adjust for potential
207 confounders via standardized mortality ratio weighting. Finally, we used a generalized linear
208 regression model in the weighted study population to estimate contraception failure rates (i.e.,
209 number of failures per 1000 person-years of follow up) and calculated the rate ratio for
210 contraception failure, directly comparing DRSP and LNG cohorts. Two differences between PBPK
211 and RWD analysis need clarification; First, we did not exclude patients with concomitant use of
212 other CYP3A modifiers; however, this factor is expected to be reasonably similar between the
213 study groups and may impose little residual confounding in risk estimates as observed in our

214 previous study.¹⁶ Second, we did not restrict the study sample to patients with CHC products
215 containing 0.15 mg LNG to have more study power and estimate the real-world risk in the
216 population.

217 Results

218 The PBPK simulations reproduced the observed central tendency and between subject variability
219 in DRSP systemic exposure after intravenous and oral administrations to young women (Figure
220 2). The results summarized in Tables S3 and S4 show the PK parameters for the 0.5 mg I.V. and
221 2 mg P.O. doses of DRSP, respectively. Since SIM/OBS ratios satisfied the acceptance criteria
222 of within 1.25-fold for prediction error for both dosage forms, the internal validity of the model was
223 confirmed. DRSP PBPK model performance and credibility were also assessed outside the limits
224 of the training dataset. The external validation of the DRSP-only model is shown in Figure 3 and
225 Table S5, which show the model was able to reproduce the mean and interindividual variability of
226 DRSP exposure in postmenopausal women with BMI > 25 kg/m². The accuracy of the derived
227 DRSP fm_{CYP3A4} was further interrogated by integrating the progestin-only PBPK model with
228 developed and validated PBPK models for EE, ketoconazole and rifampicin.^{2,3} The simulated
229 DRSP peak (C_{max}) and extent of exposure (AUC), in the presence and absence of perpetrators,
230 as well as the AUCR were consistent with observed values in the respective clinical studies^{6,9,10},
231 as shown in Tables S6, S7. In case of the DRSP-EE PBPK model (Figure 4), simulations
232 reproduced DRSP PK after single and multiple doses, including the increased interindividual
233 variability observed at the late phase of the therapeutic regimen after dosing cessation (*i.e.* CV%
234 of AUC_{0-1 day} = 23% versus CV% of AUC_{21-24 day} = 41%). Furthermore, predicted and observed
235 AUCR values resulting from DDIs involving DRSP and EE with ketoconazole or rifampicin met
236 the acceptance criteria of 1.25-fold for prediction error (Table S7), confirming the adequacy of the
237 derived DRSP fm_{CYP3A4}.

238 The impact of efavirenz on DRSP and LNG systemic exposures, administered in combination with
239 EE, did not differ when the contraceptive was administered via a single (scenario 1) or multiple
240 doses (scenario 2). On the other hand, the magnitude of the impact of carbamazepine on the PK
241 of the victim drugs was dependent on the dosing regimen due to the auto-induction PK properties
242 of carbamazepine (Table 2). When single doses of the CHCs, DRSP-EE or LNG-EE, were

243 administered to virtual subjects already receiving carbamazepine 400 mg QD during 21 days
244 (scenario 1), the magnitude of the simulated DDIs was approximately 20% lower in comparison
245 to the results obtained for the simulated clinical trial in the scenario 2 (Table 2). The similar trend
246 observed for both progestins, in terms of increasing the magnitude of carbamazepine-mediated
247 DDI after multiple doses of the CHCs, suggests that EE, a common element in both CHCs and a
248 CYP3A4 inhibitor, may affect the exposure of carbamazepine. In fact, simulated carbamazepine
249 extent of exposure at the last dosing interval was approximately 25% higher after multiple
250 administrations of the CHCs in comparison to the single dose regimens.

251 Co-administration of DRSP with inhibitors and inducers resulted in PK changes of approximately
252 1.5- to 3-fold (Table 2). The estimated ratios of exposure show a higher impact of CYP3A4
253 inducers on DRSP exposure in comparison to LNG, which is qualitatively in-line with the
254 contribution of CYP3A4 to the metabolism of both progestins (Table 2). For example, the impact
255 of carbamazepine was 25% higher on DRSP PK in comparison to LNG.

256 In the RWD study, we identified 17,039 subjects in the LNG cohort and 15,254 subjects in the
257 DRSP cohort who were using concomitant CYP3A4-inducing antiepileptic drugs. The mean age
258 was 29 ± 10 years and 27 ± 9 years, respectively, and the demographic and clinical characteristics
259 of the study population had minor imbalances at baseline (Table S8). The propensity scores
260 showed excellent overlapping distributions between study cohorts and the generated sample
261 weights were within acceptable range (Figure S3), which allowed for successful adjustment for
262 confounders. After weighting, baseline characteristics were well balanced, reflected in absolute
263 standardized differences below 10% for all characteristics (Figure S3; Table S8). The rate ratio of
264 contraception failure was 1.53 among patients taking DRSP and CYP3A4-inducing antiepileptic
265 drugs in comparison to patients under the same circumstances but taking LNG (Table 3).

266 Discussion

267 In this study, we developed and validated a PBPK model for DRSP in a stepwise fashion. First,
268 we determined the relative contribution of CYP3A4 to the metabolic clearance of DRSP from a
269 reported clinical DDI study.⁶ A DRSP $f_{mCYP3A4}$ of approximately 65% was back-calculated from *in*
270 *vivo* data and used for subsequent modeling steps, including definition of CYP3A4-mediated
271 intrinsic clearance. The disposition model was developed using individual-level PK data available
272 publicly for a DRSP-only solution administered intravenously in young women.⁹ Subsequently,
273 the absorption-related component of the PBPK model was developed, also leveraging publicly
274 available individual-level PK data.⁹ Model performance and credibility were assessed using a
275 dataset not used during model development. Since the model captured DRSP systemic exposure
276 after intravenous and oral administration of DRSP to postmenopausal women, model adequacy
277 was concluded. External validity of the DRSP PBPK model was comprehensively interrogated
278 using clinical data available in the literature. The DRSP PBPK model was further integrated with
279 a previously validated EE PBPK model, resulting in a CHC PBPK model.² The CHC PBPK model
280 was further combined with developed and validated PBPK models for ketoconazole or rifampicin
281 and applied to inform DDI simulations. Predicted AUCR values were within 1.25-fold of the
282 observed ones, confirming the adequacy of the derived DRSP $f_{mCYP3A4}$.

283 Once independently developed and validated, PBPK models for DRSP (or LNG), EE,
284 carbamazepine and efavirenz were combined in simulations to evaluate the impact of study
285 design on the magnitude of resulting metabolic DDIs.² To this end, we evaluated two different
286 scenarios that are relevant for drug development and regulatory assessment as well as clinical
287 practice. The results showed that, in the case of mutual DDIs where victim drugs also affect the
288 metabolism of the inhibitor/inducer, dosing both victim and perpetrator to the steady state would
289 allow the assessment of a more complex interaction network. For example, when co-administered
290 with EE, progestin PK seems to be time-dependent, e.g. $AUC_{\tau,SS} / AUC_{inf}$ is 1.25 for DRSP and
291 2.4 for LNG. Furthermore, our simulations suggest that EE seems to mitigate carbamazepine

292 auto-induction of its metabolism by competitively inhibiting CYP3A4 at high steady state
293 concentrations. Therefore, our findings agree with the current clinical DDI guideline issued by the
294 FDA, which recommends that multiple-dose administration of the substrate and a perpetrator
295 should be studied in case of time-dependent PK.¹³

296 Exploring cases at the limits of the variable range of certain design factors is a common practice
297 in regulatory science and it is generally referred to as a exposure-bracketing approach.¹⁷ In this
298 research, we carried out virtual DDI studies using strong inhibitors and inducers of CYP3A4 to
299 identify the lower and upper boundaries for the impact of metabolic DDIs on DRSP and LNG
300 systemic exposure, defining progestin-specific exposure-bracketing for CHC. In the case of
301 DRSP, predicted AUCR values ranged from approximately 0.2 to 2.2 when DRSP was co-
302 administered with the known strongest inducer (rifampicin) or inhibitor (ketoconazole) of CYP3A4,
303 respectively, in line with clinical observations.^{6,10,18} The exposure-bracketing for LNG ranges from
304 approximately 0.4 to 1.5 in the presence of rifampicin or ketoconazole, respectively.² These
305 intervals represent the design space within which DRSP and LNG PK will be altered when they
306 are co-administered with any other CYP3A4 perpetrator. Such results confirm previous findings
307 that inducers more significantly impact progestin PK compared to inhibitors.² Since CYP3A4
308 inhibition rarely result in safety events in CHCs but strong CYP3A4 inducers may significantly
309 affect the efficacy profile of progestins (i.e. AUC values decreased by 60-80% when co-
310 administered with rifampicin), we focused on the lower boundary of the exposure-bracketing, in
311 line with current regulatory guideline.³

312 When LNG 100 µg and EE 30 µg are co-administered with rifampicin, simulated mean LNG trough
313 concentration at steady state was approximately 500 ng/L in healthy BMI women.^{2,19} This
314 simulated value is still higher than the modeled average threshold levels of LNG required for
315 achieving perfect-use Pearl Index values of 2-3 after oral administration, i.e. ranging from 175 to
316 410 ng/L.¹⁹ In turn, for DRSP 3 mg and EE 30 µg co-administered with rifampicin, mean DRSP
317 trough concentration at steady state was approximately 900 ng/mL.³ However, DRSP exposure-

318 response model is yet to be developed and since it is not available as implant formulations , the
319 same benchmark-based rationale cannot be applied.

320 When comparing the incidence rate of unintended pregnancy in the RWD with the relative change
321 in exposure in the presence of strong CYP3A4 inducers in two independent work streams,
322 respective ratios (i.e. hazard ratio for RWD (53% risk increase) versus AUC ratio (AUCR) in the
323 presence and absence of CYP3A4 induction for exposure (25% exposure ratio increase))
324 suggest the same direction of impact when benchmarking DRSP to LNG. This suggests that
325 differences in exposure between our two extreme case progestins translate into real-world
326 outcomes. A linear relationship between plasma exposure change (AUCR) and contraceptive
327 failure for CHCs may not be expected given the additional sources of variability and efficacy
328 captured in RWD analyses. In addition, future research is needed to define efficacy thresholds
329 with respect to progestin plasma levels. However, the unique integration of PBPK and RWD
330 analysis provided at least partial mechanistic explanation for approximately half of the
331 contraception failures observed in the real-world cohort. Additional research on the clinical
332 relevance of the simulated changes in the systemic exposure of DRSP and LNG are conducted
333 using model-based meta-analysis and real-world pharmacoepidemiologic studies by different
334 stakeholders involved in this multidisciplinary collaborative effort with the objective of evaluating
335 the impact of DDIs on the efficacy and safety of hormonal contraceptive agents.

336 **Conclusion**

337 Both, PBPK modeling and RWD analysis, demonstrate that use of CYP3A4 inducers increases
338 the risk of unintended pregnancy more in women taking DRSP containing hormonal
339 contraceptives compared to those with LNG. This risk increased in the presence of CYP3A4
340 inducers with higher induction potential (rifampicin > efavirenz > carbamazepine). These results
341 establish that within class (i.e., within progestins) differences exist in susceptibility to DDIs.
342 Specifically, our results further support the CHCs label recommendations that use of backup or
343 alternate methods of contraception may be required to minimize the risk of unintended
344 pregnancies, especially with DRSP containing hormonal contraceptives in the presence of
345 CYP3A4 inducers.

346

347 **Study Highlights**

348 What is the current knowledge on the topic?

349 Hormonal contraceptives are a widely used class of drugs throughout the world. The clearance
350 of the progestin component of oral combined hormonal contraceptives (CHCs) are mediated by
351 CYP3A4, thus there is risk for drug-drug interactions when given concomitantly with CYP3A4
352 perpetrators.

353 What question did this study address?

354 What is the CYP3A4 DDI extent of a high $f_{m_{CYP3A4}}$ progestin, drospirenone, and how does this
355 compare to a relatively low $f_{m_{CYP3A4}}$ progestin, levonorgestrel?

356 What does this study add to our knowledge?

357 By understanding the PK alteration risk of high and low $f_{m_{CYP3A4}}$ progestins in DDI scenarios, a
358 broad understanding of progestin-based DDI risk is elucidated due to this within-class
359 bracketing approach.

360 How might this change clinical pharmacology or translational science?

361 Applications of this work's results can provide a deeper perspective on how to mitigate
362 contraceptive DDI risks and optimize future product development.

363

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367

368 **Conflict of Interest**

369 J.H. and T.W. are employees of Bayer AG. All other authors declare no competing interests for
370 this work.

371

372 **Author Contributions**

373 BC, LS, RC, SS, VV, TW, JH, AS, and JB wrote the manuscript, SS, RC, VV, AW, TW and JB
374 designed the research, BC, LS, AS, KL, SK, MP, and RC performed the research, BC, LS, AS,
375 and RC analyzed the data.

376

377

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434 **Figure Legends**

435 **Figure 1.** Stepwise modeling workflow. CYP = cytochrome P450; IV = intravenous; AUCR = ratio
436 between area under the concentration vs time curve observed with and without perpetrators; EE
437 = ethinyl estradiol; CHC = combined hormonal contraceptive.

438 **Figure 2.** Model development. (A) Simulated DRSP $f_{m_{CYP3A4}}$ (progestin only) Predicted and
439 observed plasma concentrations after administering DRSP intravenously (0.5 mg as a bolus; B)
440 and orally (2 mg; C) to eight young women (Age 20-35 years old; BMI 18 – 24 kg/m²).

441 **Figure 3.** Model validation. Predicted and observed plasma concentrations after administering
442 DRSP intravenously (2 mg as a bolus; B) and orally (3 mg; C) to six postmenopausal women (Age
443 55-65 years old; BMI 25 – 31 kg/m²).

444 **Figure 4.** Model validation. Predicted and observed plasma concentrations after administering
445 the combined hormonal contraceptive (DRSP 3 mg + EE 0.03 mg) QID to young women for 21
446 days (Age 20-35 years old; BMI 18 – 24 kg/m²).

447

448 **Supplementary Information**

449 Supplemental Materials.docx

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